

PROBLEMS OF UZBEK LEARNERS WITH USING SUBORDINATING CONJUNCTIONS WHILE MAKING COMPLEX SENTENCES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article covers problematic areas of using and learning subordinating conjunctions for Uzbek learners while making complex sentences in English language and presents possible solutions.

Key words: adverbial clauses, conjunctions, interlanguage inferences, effective ways, complex sentences, dependent and independent clauses.

Language teaching does not always mean teaching particular grammar point with latest effective methods or approaches. This process also involves finding out weaknesses and improvement areas of L1 and putting the main emphasis on them. This article covers Uzbek learners` problematic areas of using conjunctions while making complex sentences with an adverbial clause in English language and ways to teach them comparatively with Uzbek language. Majority of Uzbek intermediate learners have a good understanding of complex sentences and adverbial clauses in English language but they don`t usually use them neither in classroom settings or daily conversation as a part of their active vocabulary and even though they attempt to use them, they tend to make systematic grammar mistakes. In other words, even if they know certain rules, they find it challenging to make use of them in their communication while connecting clauses in complex sentences. Having analyzed different learners` mistakes in this point, it is found that many language learners are practically unintelligible to connect the clauses of complex sentences, mainly contrasting and reasoning clauses.

First of all, it is important to analyze why teaching adverbial clauses is important for L2 learners.

They play crucial role in the creation of complex sentences and coherent discourse markers in English language. As Robert Y.(2006) defined dependent clauses cannot be sentences on their own and for that reason they are depend on an independent clause in order to support them. According to him, the independent clause in a complex sentence carries the main meaning of the sentence and either

clause may come first. Additionally, adverbial clauses are dependent clauses that modify or give more information about a verb in the independent clause.

Next important point to consider is why using subordinating conjunctions is problematic for Uzbek learners. Initially, some language instructors do not have full understanding of the ways of teaching them appropriately and they put less emphasize on practice or produce part of their lessons. In other words, they are not introduced in context or not taught enough explicitly with inductive teaching approach. With regard to the main issues from learners` perspective, they consider that learning all the types of clauses is very complicated and without applying them in practice, it is very challenging for them. Some L2 learners fail to differentiate contrast and reason conjunctions with prepositions as using Subejct+verb structure after prepositions as well instead of using noun or –ING forms. The common mistakes are:

The match was cancelled because of it was raining .

I drink a bottle of water for health reasons despite I don` t like it.

The buses were all running late in the city owing to the weather was very bad.

Furthermore, while making complex sentences with an adverbial clause of course with as, since, because, it may be postpositional and prepositional based on the rheme and other requirements, while in Uzbek they are usually postpositional and the usage of “since” mainly cause difficulties for Uzbek learners.

Besides that, they have problems with differentiating grammatical structures of contrast and reason conjunctions and it causes to use them unconsciously with grammar errors. Moreover, it is crucial to mention the difficulties related to the position of conjunctions in Uzbek and English languages and interlanguage interferences when Uzbek students speak English. Take as an example of the complex sentences with an adverbial clause of condition which are the most difficult for Uzbek students.

With regard to the solutions above mentioned issues, one of the most effective ways of teaching clauses of contrast and reason is the usage of consciousness-raising technique in an interactive way for Uzbek learners. To provide efficient learning environment for acquiring this grammar point several method and approaches can be used in teaching grammar. First of all, as Schmidt(1994) pointed out in his Noticing Hypothesis, it is crucial to create sufficient condition in order to take place input for learning. When learners are involved in language acquisition through noticing tasks, they stay engaged throughout the learning process and actively participate in the lesson as providing learner-centered classroom. The warm up stage of the lesson promotes student-discovery based on their schemata of connecting clauses. According to Ellis(1997), by noticing tasks, learners attend consciously to

form or meaning and through this way they become aware of specific language features. Possible method and approaches to teach grammar are TBLT, PPP and as well as inductive approach is implemented with authentic materials.

To conclude, with an increasing demand of language learning for Uzbek learners, it is important to take into account problematic areas of L2 acquisition. In this regard, finding out weaknesses of Uzbek learners while making complex sentences and implementing possible solutions is crucial than ever before.

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